

Title: Ex SPSS Trainer with 12 years of experience in Statistics and Data Mining

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INTRODUCTION:

Built 10 over prediction models in a local Telco to profile, find next product to purchase and understand what Telco products to sell to customers based on URL and App browsing behaviour

AIM:

To find potential customers who will use more mobile data, extend their services to paid TV and broadband and their URL and App browsing behaviour.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The prediction models which are running live now on targeted campaigns are

- 1) C5 decision tree for profiling and predict customers who will use more mobile data.
- 2) APRIORI which predicts the TV channels they will purchase based on the mobile services they are using.
- 3) K-means to group the customers' URL and App Genre to know their URL and Apps browsing behaviour.

RESULTS:

The prediction models are going live and earning more revenue for the Telco and scoring their customers 24/7.

CONCLUSIONS:

This also allows their marketing team to mix and match prediction targets strategies for customized selling which in turns increases their ROI and competitiveness in the Telco market.

KEYWORDS:

Prediction, Big Data, Decision Tree, Clustering, Market Basket Analysis

BIOGRAPHY:

Jarrod is an ex SPSS trainer who has 12 years of experience in building prediction models. He had experiences in building prediction models in banking, insurance, Government, e-commerce, Telco and mobile phone industry. As he was an SPSS trainer, he had taught Statistics and Data Mining for 3 years to 3,000 over professionals.